

Evaluation of C-V2X devices to deploy a C-ITS information distributor system based on a V2I2V architecture

Lluc Feixa-Morancho*, Pau Feixa-Morancho*, Marc Codina*, Jordi Marias-i-Parella*[†], Jordi Casademont^{†*}, Bruno Cordero*, Francisco Vazquez-Gallego*, Jesus Alonso-Zarate*
*i2CAT Foundation, Barcelona, Spain.

[†]Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona, Spain; Email: bruno.cordero@i2cat.net

Abstract—To facilitate the widespread adoption of Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) and applications, deploying infrastructure alongside roadways to support vehicle communication becomes imperative. This infrastructure, leveraging Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC), necessitates communication infrastructure integrating two technologies: cellular networks and C-V2X (Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything), thus embracing a Vehicle-to-Infrastructure-to-Vehicle (V2I2V) approach. This paper presents an analysis of various Road-Side Units (RSUs) devices from different manufacturers to be used in these architectures, focusing on two key aspects. Firstly, their user-friendliness to enable programming for seamless integration with the communication protocol stack executed in the MEC. Secondly, their ability to meet the transmission capacity demands in high-density scenarios.

Index Terms—Vehicular communications, V2X, C-ITS, V2I2V, CCAM, RSU, LTE-PC5

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a surge of interest in Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) and the accompanying services facilitated by Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS). Regarding vehicle connectivity, notable strides have been made in protocol architectures, with the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) ITS protocol architecture based on GeoNetworking (GN) and Basic Transport Protocol (BTP) leading in Europe, and the Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE) protocol architecture championed by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE), and National Transportation Communications for Intelligent Transportation Systems (NTCIP) in the USA. The evolution of radio technology for Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) communication has advanced from IEEE 802.11p to the newer version, 802.11bd, and has been complemented, or de facto being substituted, by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project's (3GPP) Long Term Evolution (LTE)-based C-V2X (Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything), technically referred to as LTE-PC5, culminating in the latest 5G New Radio (NR)-V2X [1].

Despite these advancements, widespread commercialization of ITS services remains elusive. One factor contributing to this could be the hesitance within the vehicle industry to fully embrace radio standards, possibly due to concerns regarding

performance metrics such as coverage, message transmission frequency, and bandwidth. In response, the alternative paradigm Vehicle-to-Infrastructure-to-Vehicle (V2I2V) communication has emerged. This approach offers several advantages compared to the V2V approach, including leveraging infrastructure for enhanced services (collision detection, traffic management, ITS information distribution, ...), amalgamating data from diverse sources (C-ITS messages or recognition of vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) through video cameras), and fostering interoperability among different radio technologies, including cellular networks.

Currently, the European project PODIUM [2], along with the former CAMEL [3], present infrastructure architectures aimed at addressing this challenge. Their high-level designs consist of three fundamental layers. The foundational layer encompasses the road system, comprising radio equipment such as Road-Side Units (RSUs) capable of complying with C-V2X, IEEE 802.11p, or both, alongside cellular networks, as well as vehicle equipment, including On-Board Units (OBUs). The intermediate layer constitutes the Edge layer, leveraging Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to deliver ITS services and serve as a gateway for various radio technologies within limited geographical regions. Lastly, the topmost layer features a central cloud infrastructure responsible for consolidating pertinent data from different MEC servers.

When focusing on communication aspects, the primary goal is to disseminate awareness and perception information to a broad array of vehicles. In Europe, awareness is facilitated by the ETSI's ITS service known as Cooperative Awareness basic service, which shares vehicles' variable parameters (position, speed, direction, ...) and fixed parameters (vehicle size, type, ...) through Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs). Perception information is conveyed by the Collective Perception Service within Collective Perception Messages (CPMs), which include objects detected by vehicles. Additionally, a plethora of other C-ITS messages exist to communicate temporal road events, traffic light phases, suggested maneuvers, among others. These messages can originate from diverse sources, including vehicles using various radio technologies and road operators. Typically, incoming information is consolidated in a database known as the Local Dynamic Map (LDM) before

being redistributed to vehicles, using all available technologies to maximize reach [4].

A significant concern with this solution lies in scalability on two fronts. Firstly, there's the challenge of receiving the vast volume of CAM messages generated by vehicles and redistribute them using fewer messages. This can be achieved through aggregating information from multiple CAMs into fewer CPM messages, treating vehicles as detected objects by the infrastructure. During this aggregation process, there's an opportunity to filter and even personalize the information in various ways [5].

The second concern revolves around avoiding saturation of the radio channel. The two primary technologies under consideration, 5G and C-V2X, operate differently in this regard. RSUs based on C-V2X utilize broadcast addressing to transmit C-ITS messages, whereas 5G networks have to rely on unicast, necessitating the transmission of individual copies of the same C-ITS message to each vehicle within the service area. Although 4G networks have standardized the evolved Multimedia Broadcast Multicast Services (eMBMS) and 5G networks support Multicast and Broadcast Service (MBS), these facilities are not typically provided by mobile operators. As a result, a hybrid deployment may offer a viable solution. In regions with low vehicle density, cellular networks could be preferable due to their broader coverage. Conversely, in densely populated areas, deploying RSUs might prove to be a more scalable solution, and also a solution for areas where cellular network coverage is deficient, or in cross-border regions where vehicles encounter that roaming between different cellular operators leads to intermittent unavailability.

In this context, we propose an edge layer deployed within a MEC server capable of receiving CAM messages transmitted by vehicles via cellular networks and C-V2X radio. This MEC server decodes CAMs, stores pertinent information in the LDM, filters relevant awareness and perception data for vehicles within the served area, aggregates this information into CPMs, incorporates GN and BTP headers, and transmits them downlink using both cellular networks and C-V2X RSUs.

Our focus in this analysis lies particularly on the functionality of these RSUs. They must possess the agility to receive all CAMs generated by vehicles, forward them to the MEC and conversely broadcast all CPMs generated by the MEC for reception by vehicles. We aim to assess their capacity for transmitting and receiving C-ITS messages per second, depending on their PC5 interface configuration. Additionally, we seek to evaluate different manufacturers to identify equipment that is configuration-friendly and allows for low-level interaction, enabling parameter customization.

Commercial equipment (OBUs and RSUs) typically serves two functions: basic radio transmission and reception, and the additional encoding and decoding of C-ITS messages using the required ITS communication protocols. However, we argue that encoding/decoding functions are better suited for the MEC due to its superior computational capabilities and ability to orchestrate load balancing during high-load scenarios. Thus, we have developed a complete ETSI ITS communication protocol

stack executed within the MEC, while RSUs solely forward messages between the fixed communication interface based on the Internet Protocol (IP) and the C-V2X radio interface, in both directions. Hence, our interest lies in equipment enabling this functionality and based on an open platform.

This paper presents our main conclusions regarding the selection of a specific manufacturer for equipment and the performance results obtained, showcasing their current capabilities for transmitting and receiving, measured in terms of packets per second (p/s). The structure of the paper is as follows: following this introduction, we outline our main requirements and conduct an analysis of C-V2X device manufacturers. In the third section, we detail the test-bed setup and the configuration process for the selected devices. Subsequently, in the fourth section, we present the performance results obtained. Finally, we conclude with our findings and implications.

II. SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

The system requirements for C-V2X devices are categorized into two groups. The first group comprises qualitative aspects concerning the user-friendliness of the equipment, particularly its programmability for performing forwarding functionalities without relying on the manufacturer's ITS communication protocol stack. The second category involves quantitative performance metrics, specifically the device's capacity for receiving and transmitting a specified volume of p/s. Initially, we evaluate three manufacturers to determine the suitability of their RSUs for performing the first group of requirements. Based on these results, we select one manufacturer. Subsequently, we assess the volume of C-ITS messages the chosen device must manage. In section IV, we test the device's ability to meet this requirement.

A. Qualitative analysis of C-V2X devices

Several manufacturers offer C-V2X devices in the market [6]. In our evaluation process, we tested products from Cohda Wireless, Commsignia, and Lacroix City. Our focus was on identifying devices with the following functionalities: the ability to access the device via SSH, tools for testing transmission performance, ease of compiling programs in languages like C, C++, or Python, access to the Application Programming Interface (API) for direct interaction with the C-V2X / PC5 interface, and the capability to transmit messages without reliance on the manufacturer's ITS communication protocol stack. We evaluated both RSUs and OBUs.

V2V and V2I Neavia Units from Lacroix City:

- Access to the device with SSH: Not available. This disqualifies this manufacturer from consideration. Their products are primarily oriented towards high-level users, as all commands must pass through an application layer, with no option to program anything within the device itself.

ITS-OB4 / ITS-RS4 from Commsignia:

- Access to the device with SSH: Yes.

- Applications for testing transmission parameters: Yes, they offer commands like `cv2x_tx_app`, `cv2x_rx_app` or `acme` to transmit test messages, receive them or act as a proxy.
- Possibility to compile programs inside the device: No, Commsignia units have read-only file systems configured without the basic tools to compile or install programs such as `gcc` and `g++` compilers or the basic `apt` Linux command. This introduces high complexity to develop programs on these units. However, Commsignia provides an SDK to cross-compile applications for dedicated use-cases but it does not provide access to low-level C-V2X radio APIs.
- Access to the API of the PC5 interface: Yes, through the Telematics Software Development Kit (SDK) offered by Qualcomm [7]. However, the absence of tools for cross-compiling applications is a notable limitation. Enabling the PC5 radio for transmission with a non-vendor-specific stack demands significant effort. This encompasses establishing a cross-compiling environment, determining the original version of the Telematics SDK used, and identifying and locating dependencies for both the application processor architecture and the firmware associated with the chipset (Qualcomm 9150).
- Possibility to transmit messages without using the manufacturer's V2X communication protocol stack: Yes, using the command `acme` or programming an application using the Telematics SDK [7] with the method provided before.
- Possibility to easily change the configuration of the PC5 channel: Yes, using configuration files.

MK6 OBU / MK6 RSU from Cohda Wireless:

- Access to the devices with SSH: Yes.
- Applications for testing transmission parameters: Yes, they offer commands like `cv2x_tx_app`, `cv2x_rx_app` or `acme` to transmit test messages, receive them or act as a proxy.
- Possibility to compile programs inside the device: Yes. It is possible to download the compilers using `apt` and from this point, it is possible to compile and execute programs in the device.
- Access to the API of the PC5 interface: Yes, using the Telematics SDK provided by Qualcomm [7].
- Possibility to transmit messages without using the manufacturer's V2X communication protocol stack: Yes, using the command `acme` or programming an application using the Telematics SDK.
- Possibility to easily change the configuration of the PC5 channel: Yes, using configuration files.

Among the tested manufacturers, Cohda Wireless emerged as the most user-friendly option, with their MK6 OBU / RSU. The primary factor is their provision of an open platform based on Linux, facilitating the installation of software packages. This capability allows for the installation of compilers and execution of any program, granting access to all network interfaces, including the PC5 interface. For these reasons, we

have selected the MK6 devices for our system. We are now proceeding with performance tests to ascertain if these devices can achieve the necessary transmission and reception rates.

The key specifications that are particularly relevant for our testing purposes are exactly the same for the MK6 RSU and OBU devices, in particular [8]: the CPU is a NXP i.MX 8 (8544 DMIPS) operating at 800MHz, the operating system is an Ubuntu LTS, they have 1GB SDRAM, 16GB eMMc of flash memory, and the main storage is an 8GB microSD Card supporting SDHC/SDXC, finally, the C-V2X Chipset is the Qualcomm SA515M.

B. Performance requirements (size and transmission rate)

Among the various standardized C-ITS messages, CAMs transmitted by vehicles stand out as the most frequently transmitted, typically occurring at a frequency of 10 Hz per vehicle. Our objective is to collect these CAMs using the RSUs in our architecture and transmit their pertinent information within CPMs, also disseminated by the RSUs. Thus, our first focus lies in determining the sizes of CAMs and CPMs.

CAM messages contain numerous optional fields. If we consider a CAM with the minimum required mandatory headers plus position, velocity, acceleration, and dimensions, once encapsulated within GN and BTP headers, along with the addition of a digital certificate and serialization for transmission, the average size is approximately 170 bytes. In contrast, a CPM necessitates approximately 118 bytes for mandatory headers, GN, BTP, and the digital certificate, plus an additional 22 bytes per announced object, which in our case represents the information of a known vehicle. Consequently, a CPM containing information for 4 vehicles has a length of 206 bytes, while for 17 vehicles, it's 492 bytes, and for 40 vehicles, it's 998 bytes. Based on these calculations, we have decided to employ test message lengths of 100, 200, 500 and 1000 bytes.

The PC5 interface transmission channel is organized into a resource grid structured across time and frequency domains. In the time domain, the resource grid is partitioned into subframes, each spanning 1 millisecond. In the frequency domain, within every subframe, the grid is further divided into physical Resource Blocks (RBs). The number of RBs per subframe depends on the available channel bandwidth. With our system utilizing a channel bandwidth of 10 MHz, we have 50 RBs per subframe.

RBs within the same subframe are grouped into subchannels. Each subchannel comprises both control information and user data. The control portion, known as the Sidelink Control Information (SCI), occupies 2 RBs. The group of RBs carrying user data in a subchannel is referred to as the Transport Block (TB). In our configuration, the SCI and TB are arranged in adjacent positions within the same subframe.

We have opted to test three different configurations based on the number of RBs per subchannel (for a more detailed understanding, please refer to [9]):

- 50 RBs per subchannel, allowing for 1 subchannel per subframe (in the tables named as 1x50).

- 10 RBs per subchannel, allowing for 5 subchannels per subframe (in the tables named as 5x10).
- 5 RBs per subchannel, allowing for 10 subchannels per subframe (in the tables named as 10x5).

Each RB within the PC5 interface can be modulated using Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK) or 16-state Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (16QAM) and employing various Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCS). These two parameters are combined into a single parameter known as the Transport Block Size Index (I_{TBS}). I_{TBS} values determine the robustness of the radio modulation and the coding rate. Lower I_{TBS} values signify more robust communication, resulting in messages being correctly received over longer distances, albeit with fewer payload bits per fixed-size TB transmitted. Reference [10] provides typical distance ranges achievable with different MCS values and [11] specifies the number of payload bits per TB depending on the I_{TBS} value.

The default configuration file of MK6 devices suggest to use MCS values ranging from 5 to 11 for vehicles traveling at speeds below 120 km/h, and MCS values ranging from 0 to 7 for vehicles traveling above this threshold. For our tests, we adhere to the MCS values 5, 7 and 11.

As per [11], the maximum number of bits that can be transmitted in our largest TB, which consists of 48 RB, is for MCS5, 4264 bits, for MCS7, it is 5992 bits, and for MCS11, it is 8504 bits. Therefore, within our range of test message lengths, messages up to 500 bytes can be transported by any MCS, while messages of 1000 bytes can only be accommodated with MCS11.

Given that the grid configuration defines subframes of 1 ms, the 1x50RB configuration can transmit a maximum of 1000 p/s. Additionally, message sizes of 500 bytes and 1000 bytes require a significant number of RBs in any considered MCS, thereby allowing also a maximum transmission rate of 1000 p/s. On the other hand, packets of 100 and 200 bytes in configurations of 5x10RB and 10x5RB can accommodate more than one packet per subframe. Consequently, the maximum theoretical limit of transmitted p/s exceeds 1000. Specifically, table I illustrates those combinations capable of theoretically transmitting more than 1000 p/s.

TABLE I
COMBINATIONS OF RESOURCE GRID, MCS NUMBER AND PACKET SIZES THAT ENABLE TO TRANSMIT MORE THAN 1000 P/S

Length (Bytes)	Theoretical maximum packets / second					
	MCS5		MCS7		MCS11	
	5x10	10x5	5x10	10x5	5x10	10x5
100	2000	3000	5000	5000	5000	5000
200	1000	2000	2000	3000	2000	3000

Table II presents an approximation of the required transmission rates of CPMs by a single RSU in two high-density vehicle scenarios, transmitting information of every known vehicle every 100ms, employing CPM lengths close to 200, 500, and 1000 bytes, as described earlier:

a) *Urban scenario*: RSU positioned at an urban intersection tasked with disseminating information about all vehicles

Fig. 1. Testbed setup.

within a 350-meter radius along the four streets converging into the intersection. Assuming each street has four lanes, each lane is 4 meters wide, and vehicles are 4,5 meters long with a 3-meter separation between them, the total number of vehicles to be announced is 730.

b) *Highway scenario*: Consider a single RSU deployed along a highway tasked with providing information about all vehicles within a 1250-meter radius in both directions. Assuming there are four lanes per direction and vehicles are 4,5 meters long with a 12-meter separation between them, the total number of vehicles to be announced is 606.

TABLE II
APPROXIMATION OF THE REQUIRED TRANSMISSION RATE OF CPMs/SECOND

Objects per CPM	CPM length (bytes)	Required CPMs / second	
		Urban	Highway
4	206	1824	1515
17	492	429	357
40	998	182	152

III. TEST-BED SETUP

In the introduction, we outlined that there is a data flow process between the MEC server and the RSUs. In the down-link direction, the edge server constructs C-ITS messages, which are then transmitted to the RSU via UDP and IP over the transport network (Ethernet in our test-bed). The RSU subsequently forwards these messages to the PC5 channel after removing the UDP and IP headers. Conversely, in the uplink direction, the RSU receives C-ITS messages via its PC5 radio interface, encapsulates them in UDP and IP, and forwards them to the MEC server for decoding and processing.

For our testing purposes, we developed a Python application capable of generating raw packets of varying lengths and frequencies. These packets are transmitted over UDP and IP to the MK6 device for broadcast over the PC5 channel. Concurrently, when the receiving MK6 device receives these packets, relays them to another computer, which captures them using the Wireshark protocol analyzer. We have developed the test-bed of Fig. 1 simulating the whole process. Our primary objective is to assess the performance of the MK6 devices when carrying out this forwarding process, rather than focusing on factors such as channel capacity or coverage range. For this reason, MK6 devices were tested inside our lab with a separation of about 3 meters.

There are two methods for forwarding packets between a UDP socket on the IP interface and the PC5 interface in the

MK6 Cohda devices. The first method involves programming an application to interact directly with the Telematics SDK provided by Qualcomm [7] and compiling it into the OBU or RSU. However, a simpler alternative exists: utilizing the pre-existing `acme` command available in the MK6 devices.

The `acme` command offers functionality for generating and transmitting test packets, receiving them, or serving as a proxy between a UDP socket and the PC5 interface. Our focus lies on the latter capability. While we could have utilized the `acme` command solely for generating and receiving packets, our architectural design relies on the RSU serving as a proxy. Therefore, we leverage the `acme` command to fulfill this role.

To activate the proxy behaviour from the Ethernet interface, receiving in UDP port 9001, to the PC5 interface, we have to execute in the MK6 device: `acme -L 9001 -E -x eth0` meaning "proxy what is received in interface named eth0 (-x eth0), using listening UDP port 9001 (-L 9001), into an event flow channel of PC5 interface (-E)".

MK6 devices feature two distinct PC5 flow types: "Event" and "SPS". The "SPS" flow employs the Semi Persistent Scheduling procedure to reserve resources for future message transmissions, adhering to specific periodicity and byte size parameters. In contrast, the "Event" flow prioritizes immediate transmission of pending messages without reservation. In our architecture, C-ITS messages are generated by the edge server. The generation of these messages depend on the incoming awareness and perception information at the edge, the predictability of vehicle positions and the number of vehicles in the area served by the edge, so, they have variable sizes and are transmitted non-periodically. Consequently, the "Event" flow aligns better with this traffic pattern.

To activate the proxy behaviour from the PC5 interface to a UDP socket in port 9002 and being the IP address of the remote computer IP-ADDR1, we have to execute in the MK6 device `acme -R -x eth0 -X IP-ADDR1 -Y 9002` meaning "proxy what is received in interface PC5 (-R) into the outgoing interface named eth0 (-x eth0), using a transmitting UDP socket with destination address IP-ADDR1 (-X IP-ADDR1) and UDP port 9002 (-Y 9002)".

The subsequent task involves modifying the various configuration parameters of the PC5 interface. These parameters are specified within the file `/etc/v2x.xml` on the MK6 devices. Upon opening the file, one encounters a field labeled `<RadioParametersContents>` followed by a lengthy hexadecimal string representing the radio configuration encoded in UPER (Unaligned Packed Encoding Rules) format.

Firstly, it is necessary to decode this hexadecimal string and convert it into a text file. This can be achieved utilizing an ASN.1 encoder/decoder, such as the ASN.1 Playground, with support of an ASN schema provided by Cohda Wireless.

Once the text configuration file is obtained, several parameters can be adjusted. Next, the most pertinent ones along with their respective values in use are enumerated:

- Carrier frequency: EARFCN ((E-UTRA Absolute Radio Frequency Channel Number) frequency 55190, which is channel 184 (5920 MHz).
- Transmission power: Given the 3-meter distance during testing, a transmission power of 0 dBm was utilized. No discernible losses due to insufficient received power were observed.
- Number of resource blocks (RBs) on the resource grid: 50, corresponding to a channel width of 10 MHz.
- Adjacency of the SCI and TB: Adjacent.
- RBs per subchannel: 10.
- Subchannels per subframe: 5.
- Minimum MCS (Modulation and Coding Scheme) number: 5.
- Maximum MCS number: 11.
- Parameters for congestion control based on Channel Busy Ratio (CBR): As the target of the test was to obtain maximum transmission performance, it was deactivated.

After implementing the necessary modifications in the text file, it's necessary to employ the ASN.1 encoder once more to encode this file into a new hexadecimal string. Subsequently, this new string must replace the existing one within the `<RadioParametersContents>` field in the file `/etc/v2x.xml`.

Finally, applying the new configuration has to be done by executing these three consecutive commands:

- `cv2x-config -stop-v2x-mode` (to switch the radio into stop mode).
- `cv2x-config -update-config-file v2x.xml` (to update the radio configuration file).
- `cv2x-config -start-v2x-mode` (to return the radio to start mode).

IV. RESULTS

In section II-B, we assessed the requirements of RSUs, concerning the transmission of C-ITS messages, to be able to deploy an ITS infrastructure aimed at disseminating awareness and perception information among vehicles within specific scenarios. This section will now proceed to perform multiple tests to ascertain the agility of RSUs in meeting these specified requirements.

Initially, we assess the transmission capacity of MK6 devices depending on packet sizes, utilizing a clean channel environment where no other transmissions occur. Subsequently, we examine the impact of employing different resource grid configurations. Following this, we evaluate the effect of concurrent transmission and reception, wherein two devices attempt simultaneous transmission and reception to detect potential performance impacts, due to computational resources. Finally, we investigate a scenario involving two transmitters and one receiver.

A. Maximum transmission frequency in function of the message length with one single transmitter

In this initial test, we assess the Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) in a scenario featuring one transmitter and one receiver. Given their close proximity, there is negligible loss attributed to propagation factors. For this test, the channel has been configured with a resource grid of 5x10RB, and employing MCS values 5, 7 and 11. The PDR for transmission frequencies of

200 p/s and 100 p/s is always 100%, and the results for 500 p/s and 1000 p/s are presented in Table III.

TABLE III
PACKET DELIVERY RATIO (PDR)
1 TX AND 1 RX; 5x10RB
DIFFERENT MCS AND TRANSMISSION FREQUENCIES (PACKETS/SECOND)

Length (Bytes)	Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR)					
	MCS5		MCS7		MCS11	
	500p/s	1000p/s	500p/s	1000p/s	500p/s	1000p/s
100	100%	54%	100%	62%	100%	67%
200	100%	51%	100%	47%	100%	55%
500	80%	41%	93%	45%	100%	54%
1000	-	-	-	-	74%	39%

There are noteworthy results deserving of analysis. Initially, we observe no losses up to a transmission rate of 200 p/s. Consequently, we ascertain the capacity to transmit 200 p/s of 1000 bytes per message using MCS11, aligning with our predefined requirements. However, at a transmission rate of 500 p/s, losses occur across all three MCS modes when the message length approaches the maximum supported by each MCS mode. We postulate that the bottleneck stems from the processing time needed to encode messages rather than constraints within the transmission channel. Nonetheless, we meet our criteria for transmitting 500 p/s of 500 bytes per message using MCS11, albeit with a slight loss using MCS7.

An intriguing scenario arises at a transmission rate of 1000 p/s. Employing MCS11 and a configuration of 5x10RB, we expect a maximum transmission rate of 5000 p/s for packet lengths of 100 bytes and 2000 p/s for lengths of 200 bytes (as indicated in Table I). However, our observed rates are only 670 p/s and 550 p/s for the respective lengths. We hypothesize that each device might be restricted to transmitting only one packet per subframe despite the availability of additional channels in the subframe, thereby limiting the maximum achievable transmission rate to 1000 p/s. Furthermore, devices may need to allocate certain subframes for reception, further constraining the transmission rate. These specifications, crucial for understanding the observed limitations, are not readily available in Cohda Wireless or Qualcomm documentations.

B. Maximum transmission frequency in function of the configuration of the resource grid with one single transmitter

The next test aims to explore the impact of resource grid configuration, with the corresponding results outlined in Table IV. At a transmission rate of 500 p/s, we discern a trend reminiscent of the previously discussed scenario: a slight reduction in transmission rate observed with 500-bytes messages. Furthermore, at a rate of 1000 p/s, we note a tendency towards better transmission rates for the 1x50RB configuration and worse rates for 10x5RB. This implies that dividing the resource grid into more subchannels may demand increased computational workload and consequently lead to longer processing times. It's important to note that we have a single transmitter and the transmission channel is not saturated.

TABLE IV
PACKET DELIVERY RATIO (PDR)
1 TX AND 1 RX; MCS 7; DIFFERENT TRANSMISSION FREQUENCIES
(PACKETS/SECOND) AND RESOURCE GRID CONFIGURATION

Length (Bytes)	Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR)					
	500 p/s			1000 p/s		
	1x50	5x10	10x5	1x50	5x10	10x5
100	100%	100%	100%	68%	62%	58%
200	100%	100%	100%	61%	47%	45%
500	92%	93%	90%	44%	45%	44%

Fig. 2. Received p/s when transmitting and receiving or only receiving. MCS11. 5x10RB. Message length: 100 bytes. Tx frequency: 500 p/s.

C. Effect of simultaneous transmission and reception

One of the factors limiting the increase in transmission frequency lies in the processing time required for managing headers and packet serialization. To investigate this hypothesis, our next test involves a scenario where MK6 devices are both transmitting and receiving messages. Fig. 2 illustrate the received packets per second for each device.

During the transmission process, we introduce a scenario where one MK6 device halts transmission to observe its impact on the other device. Time is segmented into distinct intervals for thorough analysis. In Fig. 2, intervals A and C depict simultaneous transmission by both devices, whereas interval B shows only device labeled MK6-A transmitting, and interval D shows only MK6-B transmitting.

We observe that when both devices are transmitting and receiving at a rate of 500 p/s, each device can receive only approximately 250 p/s from the other, resulting in a PDR of only 50%. However, when only one device is transmitting, the other can receive the full 500 p/s, achieving a PDR of 100%. This observation supports our hypothesis that there is a limit in processing time, as the channel is not saturated, thereby constraining transmission to 250 p/s when both devices are active.

D. Test with two simultaneous transmitters and one receiver

The final test involves three MK6 devices: two designated solely for transmission and the other for reception. Figure 3 illustrates the p/s in the receiving device. The transmitters operate simultaneously, emitting bursts of packets of varying sizes 50, 100, 200, 500, 700, and 800 bytes. The received p/s from each transmitter are depicted by the red and green graphs, while the black line represents the summation of both.

In graph A, where each device aims to transmit 100 p/s, the receiver successfully captures all packets of small sizes. However, as packet sizes increase beyond 500 bytes, slight losses become apparent. In graph B, where each device targets a transmission rate of 500 p/s, the receiver never achieves a reception rate of 1000 p/s, even for the smallest packets. Theoretically, given the configuration of 1x50RB and MCS7, the channel should be capable of transmitting a maximum of 1000 p/s for any packet size smaller than 5992 bits. Moreover, since each packet utilizes an entire subframe, there should be no difference in terms of channel saturation across different packet sizes. If variations exist for different sizes, they likely stem from packet management computational time required.

Furthermore, in graph B, the reception from different transmitters appears to be highly complementary. When one transmitter is able to transmit numerous p/s, the other transmits very few, and vice versa. In graph C, where each device attempts to transmit 1000 p/s, theoretically saturating the channel, the maximum received p/s for small packets is approximately 750 p/s, and for large packets, it's around 500 p/s.

Finally, according to the configuration, MCS7 mode should not support the transmission of 800-byte messages. Hence, we infer that Cohda devices, despite the specified MCS in the configuration file, automatically employ a higher MCS if the message size requires it for transmission.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an evaluation of C-V2X RSUs from three different manufacturers, aiming to integrate them into a C-ITS infrastructure. This infrastructure performs encoding/decoding of the communication protocol stack within a MEC environment, enhancing computational capabilities and capitalizing on centralized information management. The evaluation reveals that Cohda Wireless devices offer the most user-friendly platform. Our study underscores the necessity for a platform facilitating direct forwarding between C-V2X and IP interfaces. Additionally, we tested that these devices provide the necessary capabilities to serve as distributors of awareness and perception information in the form of CPM messages, albeit facing limitations in CPU processing capabilities.

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Fig. 3. 1 Receiver and 2 transmitters. Red line: received p/s from one device. Green line: received p/s from the other device. Black line: total received p/s. 6 bursts of different message lengths, from left to right in bytes: 50, 100, 200, 500, 700 and 800. MCS 7. 1x50RB.

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